

Trajectories, socio-cultural functions, aesthetics of Hindi contemporary humour: an interdisciplinary approach

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Objectives of this project

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- An illustration of a stage performance. A central figure, a woman in a yellow and green sari, stands on a stage with her arms raised, gesturing. She is surrounded by several other people seated on the stage, some of whom are clapping. In the foreground, a large audience of people is seated in rows of chairs, facing the stage. The background features a simple stage set with curtains.
- To investigate forms of contemporary Hindi humour and satire.
 - To trace the grounds for an interdisciplinary study of the aesthetics behind the use of these modes
 - To analyse the socio-cultural functions of Hindi humour in Indian contemporary context.
 - To present the scope and objectives of the European funded project "FISM".

Definition of “humour” and “satire” in the present context

« Satire is the “the deliberate use of comic for purposes of attack »

(Berger 1997, p. 167)

« Satire’s own frequent formless forces it to inhabit the forms of other genres (as in the mock heroic), and makes satire resistant to simplistic versions of a formalist approach; the incongruity created by satire’s appreciation appropriation of other forms can create *friction between form and content* (emphasis is mine) that runs counter to prescriptions of formalism. »

(Connery and Combe 1995: 5)

Definition of “humour” and “satire” in the present context

« There may be proper satirical *genres*, such as the mock ode, the parody, or, moving to South Asia, possibly the *naksha*. But satire as such, I think, cannot be called a literary genre. It is rather a *mode* of expression that somewhat parasitically builds up on established literary genres; and we have good reason to call the above-mentioned examples *secondary genres*. »

(Harder 2012: 166)

Avadh Punch, A Urdu satirical journal from Lucknow, 1878, Wikimedia Commons

Satire and Humour in Indian aesthetics

« Humor in Sanskrit drama is often a kind of witty ironic repartee involving the hero, the heroine, and her friend, the go-between. The *alamkarikas* (aestheticians) consider it an accessory aesthetic mood to the erotic; they call it *narman*, often translated “joke,” though it means “wit,” or “witty gesting.” (...) Since the definitions of the *bhava* called *hasa* and its *rasa*, *hasya*, which would seem to have been traditionally retained from the *Natyashastra* all the way to the *Rasagangadhara* do not cognize this jesting, what do they cite as funny? The definitions invariably center around the notion of the *vikrta*, literally “changed, altered,” but a word commonly used in the sense of “strange,” and almost as commonly “deformed, disfigured, mutilated” -- in short: grotesque. »

(Gitomer 1991: 83-84)

Hindi satire (*vyangya*) as a specific field of Hindi literature

« Hariśankar Parsāī, Śarad Jośī, Keśavcandra Varmā, using a satirical point of view, give voice to the contradictions of their time. »

(*Nayī kahānī kī bhūmikā* 1966: 16)

« was the time of the 'Nayī kahānī' (...) I had no connection with this movement. I was not even considered a short story writer. Even literary critics and theorists had no problem calling me simply a 'satirist', and for me it was the same. »

(Hariśankar Parsāī, *Ham ik umr se vākiph haiñ*: 105)

Humour as an adaptive coping strategy

« First, satire does not really cure a morally sick world, but helps us to cope with it. This does not mean that satire cannot contribute to political change, but it only has a modest impact in the service of motivating more direct political action. Second, satire helps us deal with the limits of critique through the solace of pleasurable autotelic engrossment in entertainment, which reconnects us to an otherwise depressingly absurd world – without ignoring that we should alleviate suffering. *Third, satire develops comic and ironic coping strategies that we can fruitfully adopt and adapt in the stories we tell about ourselves in a world that is sick beyond full recovery.* (emphasis is mine) »

(Declercq 2021: 1-2)

Which adaptive coping functions expressed by satire and humour?

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- An illustration of a stage performance. A central figure, a woman in a yellow and green outfit, stands on a stage with her arms raised, gesturing. To her left, a man in a suit and glasses and a woman in a red sari are seated on a stage. To her right, a man in a white shirt and a woman in a red sari are seated, clapping. In the foreground, the backs of several audience members' heads are visible, looking towards the stage.
- Informative Functions (Paroske 2016; Zekavat 2021)
 - Embodying Political Claims (Zekavat 2017; Zekavat 2022)
 - Alleviating Psychological Sufferings (Fry 2000; Garrick 2006)
 - Satire, Humour and Marginalization (Subhangani, Shivaprasad 2023)

Satire as an instrument of psychological healing

« When treating trauma survivors, it is important to understand the nature of their humor. When recalling traumatic memories, humorous instances and acts are often left out of the counseling session due to the fear that the use of humor would be considered disrespectful to the dead and/or injured. *Thus, even though humor can help survivors see that there are still pleasures in life despite the tragedy that occurred and, therefore, can be an important part of the healing process, it is still sometimes seen as taboo.* »

(Garrick 2006)

Satire, Humour and fields of Hindi literature from the 1950s to present day

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- A faint, stylized illustration of a stage performance. A central figure, a woman in a yellow and green sari, stands with arms raised, gesturing. To her left, a man in a suit and glasses points towards her. To her right, a man in a green shirt and a woman in a red sari are clapping. In the foreground, the backs of several audience members' heads are visible, looking towards the stage.
- Short stories: *Bholārām kā jīv* (Hariśankar Parsāī)
 - Anthologies of short stories: *Vaiṣṇav kī phisalan* (Hariśankar Parsāī), *Beimānī kī parat* (Hariśankar Parsāī)
 - Literary columns: *Kabīr kharā bāzār meṃ* (Hariśankar Parsāī); *Suno bhāī sādho* (Hariśankar Parsāī); *Tulsīdās candan gisaiṃ* (Hariśankar Parsāī)
 - Autobiography: *Ham ik umr se vākiph haiṃ* (Hariśankar Parsāī)
 - Movies: *Yah jo hai zindagī* (Śarad Jośī), *Vikram aur Betāl* (Śarad Jośī)
 - Children's literature: Hariśankar Parsāī, Śarad Jośī

Hindi and its 'Mediatic' and 'Transcultural life' during the 1970s:
Hariśankar Parsāi's Imaginary Interviews *Kabīrā khaṛā bājār meṃ.*

“You do not look like that Kabīrdās. He was a weaver while you are wearing a shimmering suit and you have probably even come here by taxi. Hence, can you be Kabīrdās?” I replied: “Do not pay attention to the rumors that Māyā has scammed me and that the bride of Rām has plundered my market. I mean, I am the same Kabīrdās, but in the twentieth century. In my character, I am the same person.”

(Parsāi 1985: 70)

Satire and Humour as extra-literary forms

- Hasya kavi sammelans, Mushayras.
- Hindi/Hinglish Stand-up comedy (developed over the last 15 years).
 - Hindi Theatre.
- Nautanki and other performative traditions.

Avadh Punch, A Urdu satirical journal from Lucknow, 1878, Wikimedia Commons

The Digitalization of Satire and Humour during the COVID-19 Pandemic

- Memes as a new form of Satire and Humour; adopted in many social media as instruments having a social and informative function.
- Digitalization of traditional cultural forms connected to humour, i.e. shows performed by satirists connected to the Hasya kavi sammelans and recited during the pandemic as instruments to ‘cure’ the spread of COVID-19.
- Spread of new literary genres, which establish satirical and parodic connections to other digitalized forms of humour (Ex. *Sattū jī ke fek nyūz*, “Sattu Ji’s Fake News”, published on *Jansattā* before, during and after the end of the pandemic).
- Diminishing the difference between humour and satire. More authors consider humour as ‘something serious’.

Presentation of the main features of FISM

“FISM” means Fighting with a Smile: Satirical and Humourist Voices of Resilience from Hindi Speaking Subaltern Subjects and Communities”

It received a Maria Skłodowska-Curie Global Fellowship project funded by the European Commission in the frame of the Horizon Europe, EU’s key funding programme for research and innovation.

The project lasts for three years

Sapienza, University of Rome is the host institution of the project

UPES is the the affiliated institution of the project. Prof. Chilana will be my supervisor during the outgoing phase of the project

One of the main targets of the project is to enhance collaboration between scholars associated with European and Global institutions

Avadh Punch, A Urdu satirical journal from Lucknow, 1878,
Wikimedia Commons

Theoretical finalities of the project FISM

- 1** Investigating in an interdisciplinary way the uses of Hindi humour and satire by marginal communities to counter the idea for which comedy is characterized by an “elitarian frame of mind” (Knight 2004).
- 2** Analyzing the uses of comedy as forms to enhance the democratic participation of subjects and communities belonging to these social groups.
- 3** Satire and humour as instruments for raising awareness and resilience.

Main activities which will be realized in the course of the project

The analysis and comparison of at least five books (prose and poetry) written by Hindi literary authors, specialized or adopting satire and humour.

The participation and subsequent analysis of at least four stand-up comedy shows and one Hasya kavi sammelan/Mushayra.

The study and comparison of at least four hundred Hindi items, detected from social media, which reveal the digital use of satire and humour by marginalized groups.

The realization of five interviews with satirists.

Methodology

1. Pure **qualitative methods** will be used for the content analysis of the literary sources. The method which will be used for the critical analysis of the texts will adopt – but not be limited to – the Simpson’s model (2003). It is an integrated stylistic method considering four variables: setting, method, uptake and target— SMUT.
2. Another **pure qualitative method** will consist in interviewing some of the main actors in the field of Hindi satire. These interviews will be pursued through open-ended questions made online or in-person modality.
3. A **balanced positioning** will allow a combination of involvement and necessary detachment from the object of investigation. The PI will inform the organizers and the main satirical poets about his will to participate in the event. Further, this will require the researcher to put up open-ended questions to members of the audience before and after the event.
4. **Mixed qualitative and quantitative methods** based will be applied to the study of social media and networks.

Conclusions

Humour and Satire have been, and still are two important modes of communication present in different ambits of the so-called Hindi public sphere.

Since the 1950s, comedy has become an interdisciplinary 'language', used by artists to enact different adapting coping strategies.

This function has been confirmed during the last pandemic, when the emergence of new digitalized forms of comedy, not unlike in other geographical contexts, has also favored a critical reflection in India.

The FISM project, which adopts an interdisciplinary approach, attempts to investigate forms of humour and satire present in the contemporary cultural sphere

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**Thank
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